

Journal of Social Sciences (COES&RJ-JSS)

ISSN (E): 2305-9249 ISSN (P): 2305-9494

Publisher: Centre of Excellence for Scientific & Research Journalism, COES&RJ LLC

Online Publication Date: 1st April 2019

Online Issue: Volume 8, Number 2, April 2019

<https://doi.org/10.25255/jss.2019.8.2.327.358>

Reviewing the Literature among Human Resource Management (HRM) Practices, Total Quality Management (TQM) Practices and Competitive Advantages

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Abstract:

Due to rising importance of the human resource management and total quality management practices to develop a competitive advantage and raise the ability to compete in the market place, organizations must understand how to attract, retain, and motivate the skilled human resource. Also, organization should be good at implementing total quality management soft dimensions, in order to create competitive advantage over time. This purpose of this paper is to review the literatures that have examined the effect of human resource management practices, total quality management practices on competitive advantage.

Keywords:

Human Resource Management (HRM) Practices, Total Quality Management (TQM) Practices, Competitive Advantages.

Citation:

Obeidat, Bader; Al-Khateeb; Tawalbeh, Hadeel Fareed; Masa'deh, Ra'ed; Akour, Mohammed Ali (2019); Reviewing the Literature among Human Resource Management (HRM) Practices, Total Quality Management (TQM) Practices and Competitive Advantages; Journal of Social Sciences (COES&RJ-JSS), Vol.8, No.2, pp:327-358; <https://doi.org/10.25255/jss.2019.8.2.327.358>.

Introduction

This paper presents the underlying theoretical aspects of this study; in particular, this paper looks at the literature on human resource management practices, total quality management practices, and competitive advantage. The literature review focuses on three primary areas; the effect of HRM practices on TQM practices, the effect of HRM practices on competitive advantage, and the effect of TQM practices on competitive advantage.

Literature Review

Human Resource Management

Human resource management (HRM) includes all management decisions and practices that affect the employee of an organization (Bhatt and Reddy, 2011). There have been many definitions of human resource management used by different scholars. Daud (2006) defined HRM as a system, policy, and practices that can affect folks that work in an organization. In addition, Shahnawaz and Juyal (2006) defined Human resources management (HRM) as all decisions and practice that influence worker within organizations. De Cieri, et al. (2008, p.5) explained HRM as “the policies, practices and systems that influence employees' behavior”. While Hussain and Ahmad (2012) considered HRM to be a system that attempts to realize an active balance between the personal interests of people and their economic added value. Lastly, Burma (2014) viewed HRM is a strategic and clear approach for the organization's most valued assets behind on the employees.

Human resources management is considered to be the most important factor that helps the organization to achieve a competitive advantage (Obeidat, et al., 2012, 2013, 2014; Masa'deh, et al., 2019). This is due to the fact that managers in both public and private organizations consider human resources to be the main source of sustaining competitive advantage; this is done by having the “best of the best” human resource systems for recruiting, selecting, motivating, and efficiently managing their people (Mesch, 2010).

HRM practices are defined as “organizational activities directed at managing the pool of human resources and ensuring that the resources are employed towards the fulfillment of organizational goals” (Pankaj and Saxena, 2012, p. 671). However, it must be taken into consideration that human resource management practices are not fixed; they differ from one country to another (Ozutku and Ozturkler, 2009; Tiwari and Saxena, 2012).

A significant body of research focuses on several specific human resource management practices. Such practices include staffing, training and development, performance appraisal compensation management, safety and health, industrial relations, and recruitment and selection (Ferguson's, 2006). Singh (2009) worked on the addition of a number of HRM practices including planning, performance evaluation, career management, and rewards. Karunesh and Pankaj (2009) examined the HRM practices implemented and identified some other practices, such as employer-employee relations, recognition through rewards, culture building, career development, and benefits. Furthermore, Pahuja and Chander (2012) added a few other practices: inculcating the right skills, knowledge and attitude; having a congenial work environment; and maintaining good employee relationships. In Hussain and Ahmad (2012) work, others

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HRM practices, namely staffing, training and development, performance appraisal compensation management, safety and health, and industrial relations. In addition, Obeidat, et al., (2014) included the practices of job design, and teamwork as important HRM practices.

Based on the comprehensive literature review, this study focuses on four HRM practices; recruitment and selection, performance appraisals, training and development, and compensation and reward. The rationale behind selecting the practices is that these practices occur relatively frequently in HRM literature for manufacturing and service industries.

Recruitment and Selection

It is generally agreed by most employers that their staff is the greatest asset for their company, and thus the recruitment and selection processes are vital in ensuring that a new employee can become efficient and produce desirable result in a short time. In other word, the success of an organization depends on having the right number of staffs, with the right skills and abilities (Mark, 2014).

Various authors who studied recruitment and selection have agreed that there is a distinct different between the two, this point can be seen in both Taylor (2008) work and Rees and French (2010) studied recruitment is the process whereby an organization collects applications for a position and creates a pool of possibly fit workers, while selection includes using techniques or different methods to evaluate the applicants and choose who is best fit to the available position, and achieve management goals and legal requirements. Mondy and Noe (2013) defined recruitment as the process of pool people on a timely basis, in sufficient numbers and with suitable experiences, to apply for jobs with an organization. Selection mentions to the process of choosing the individual, who is best suited for position and for the organization. According to Khanna (2014, 148) recruitment is “a process of publicizing the vacancies of any esteemed capacity in the most attractive and rightful manner with the sole objective of attracting maximum pool of eligible candidates for the position”; while selection is “a process of sorting the most relevant job applications of candidate selection or closure”.

Recruitment and selection are shown to be crucial processes for organizations (Anyim, 2012). Human research leaders are successful in their work often know how to attract, select and retain top talent efficiently, and they also hold key information, such as on incorrect numbers and locations, at the right times (Longenecker and Fink, 2013). This process includes seeking and selecting applicants whom the recruiter foresees can be a fit for the company and can contribute the maximum performance to the organization. Both recruitment and selection are fundamental HRM activities; if managed well, these activities can have a significant impact on organizational performance, which can lead to a more positive organizational image (Pilbeam and Corbridge, 2006). By contrast, ineffective recruitment has a number of cost effects for employers, such as; low morale which can affect employee performance, lost business opportunities, as well as higher levels of labor turnover (CIPD, 2005), damage production, and customer dissatisfaction.

Recruitment and selection process normally involve creating a job advertisement based on the job analysis and the job description of a vacant position; afterwards, the position is advertised widely to attract a large number of applicants, and then the best candidate is identified using validated tests and interviews (Adetunji, 2015). Sources of recruitment may be categorized into two sections - internal and external (Aswathappa, 2008). The internal sources of recruitment comprise present employees and employee referrals; external sources of recruitment are professional associations, newspaper advertisements, unsolicited applicants, management consulting firms, and the internet (Absar, 2012). Some selection processes may consist of testing procedures while others processes may emphasize interviews and reference checks (Tabassum, 2011). Thus, the selection process differs from one organization to other, but the processes are all generally similar, which consist of the following: filling out application forms, initial tests, primary interviews, employment tests, written examinations, comprehensive interviews, reference checks, and finally a job offer (Absar, 2012).

Performance Appraisals

Performance appraisals are a key factor in improving the quality of work input and encouraging employees to be more engaged. Performance appraisals also introduce a foundation for upgrades as well as the development of an organization and employee succession plans (Shaout and Yousif, 2014).

The aim of performance appraisal is to guide and encourage the employees' activities to be in line with the organization goals (Zhu, 2010). Hence, performance appraisal is imperative to the strengthening bond between employee and employer. In addition, it is one of the important issues for companies getting successful and improving their performance (Burma, 2014). Also, it is for documenting employees' performance for legal reasons (Gordon, 2016).

Phin (2015) defined performance appraisal as a process of evaluating the performance of employees in the workplace. It contains both quantitative and qualitative aspects of employee job performance. It is a process to communicate to an employee and plan to develop for improvement. In addition, performance appraisal is also viewed as the process that affect the status of employee, such as, retention, termination, promotion, transfer, salary increase or decrease, or admission into a training program (Neeraj,2014). According to Singh (2014), performance appraisal is a systematic method for periodically evaluating job performance based on the criteria pre-established and organizational goals.

As one of the core human resource practices, performance appraisals is usually managed within an official setting in order to provide a basis for decisions that pertain to employees, improve employees' performance, and ultimately enhance the effectiveness of organizations (Kalender and Vayvay, 2015). For example, through performance appraisal results, organizations can determine the training needs of their employees by identifying the weaknesses and strengths of each employee. By doing so, organizations can determine the appropriate training programs that will help to deal with the weaknesses and to develop the strengths, thereby improving the performance level of their employees (Abu-dhaim, 2011). This point is also made by Wienclaw (2016), who

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claim that performance appraisal is one of the key functions of an organization's human resources section. Organizations use the data collected in performance appraisal systems mainly to establish standards and evaluation systems that can be used to form the basis of assessing whether employees should be rewarded for good performance or reprimanded for poor performance.

Training and Development

Training and development are important in the world of business especially in the increasing competition and challenges between the companies to survive and keep companies alive and to achieve the competitive advantage and get the best results organization must provide training and development programs that improve staff skills and also enhance their performance (Chaudhary and Bhaskar, 2016). It is one of the important ways to facilitate individual employees in learning new skills and knowledge with the goal to develop their current skill set and knowledge (Joarder, et al., 2011). Jimenez and Valle (2013) confirmed in their study that human are valuable assets of the Organization, thus, an organization needs to invest in training and development to strengthen their capacities and abilities.

The practice of training and development is defined as the process of improving the skills and develop the ability to accomplish tasks efficiently and effectively in organizations (Robert and John, 2004). In addition, this practice is considered technical use to transfer knowledge, skills and competencies to improve employee working in the current and future business performance (Parce and Robinson, 2009). In addition, Adjirackor, et al., (2016) identified training as a systematic approach that improves individual, team, and organizational effectiveness. Similarly, Noe (2010, p.24) viewed training as "to a planned effort by a company to facilitate employees' learning of job-related competencies. These competencies include knowledge, skills, or behaviors that are critical for successful job performance". This is supported by Marsíkova and Slaichova (2015) who claimed that training and development is a set of tools and methods and content to create a purposeful approach which is planned by the company's efforts to develop the competencies of their employees.

Training is considered to be the most important factor in the business sector due to the fact that training provides numerous benefits. Training develops competencies such as technical, human, conceptual and managerial for the furtherance of individual and organization growth (Kulkarni, 2013). It also increases the quality process of connection with managers and coworkers as well as teamwork ability (Vute and Farcas, 2015). With regards to employees, training creates a great job satisfaction and morale among employees and it increases salary, promotion and incentives (Chaudhary and Bhaskar, 2016). Lastly, training also enhances company productivity (Marsíkova and Slaichova, 2015).

Employee development programs are important for any organization if it wishes to remain solvent and competitive in the marketplace and leads to motivation and loyalty within their organization (Marsíkova, Slaichova, 2015). Employee development can increase organization performance (such as effectiveness, profitability, sales) and employee and customer satisfaction, and it can improve organizational reputation

(Aguinis and Kraiger, 2009). Finally, it can also increase investment on training programs to develop them for future needs (Kulkarni, 2013).

According to Dessler (2017), there are five steps in training and development process. The first step involves a testing procedure to identify the specific job performance skills required; this step appraises the trainees' skills. The second step is instructional design, which refers to how the training program content is determined, selected, and designed. There may be a third validation step, in which the defects are identified and removed from the training program by presenting it to a small representative public. The fourth step is to implement the program, by training the targeted employee group. Lastly, the final fifth step is an evaluation, in which the management appraises the program's successes or failures.

According to Littlepage, et al., (2016), there are several methods for training and development, which can be divided into several areas; cognitive, behavioral, and management development methods. Cognitive methods provide the rules on the method of doing something, and this can include using written or verbal information, or demonstrating the relationships among concepts. These methods are connected with changes in knowledge and attitude by stimulating learning, behavioral methods are concerned with giving practical training to the trainees and allowing them to behave in a real fashion. These methods are best used for skill development. And the end, management development methods are considered the most future oriented methods. And the key focus on the education of the employees. Some of these methods include exercise and sensitivity training.

Compensation and Reward

Mondy (2010) stated compensation as a combination of employees' benefits and services provided to employee in return for their service, which positively affects the retaining and motivating employees. Through Werner (2011, p. 587) represented compensation as "packages entail some basic features that tend to make employees satisfy on their job amongst which includes salaries, bonuses, incentives, allowances, promotion, recognition". In addition, Gopinath and Shibu (2016) viewed compensation as a payment received by the employee for its contribution to the organization, which is an integral part of the human resources management Gateway through the monetary and non-monetary benefits which help in motivating employees and improving the effectiveness of the organization.

Compensation has several benefits such as; the ability to achieve employee satisfaction and employee retention and increase performance in the company (Osibanjo, et al., 2014). It can also help the organization to achieve its objectives and increase its competitiveness (Beck-Krala and Scott 2014). In addition, compensation can stably and retains employees and helps in reducing labor turnover within the organization (Odunlami, 2014). Thus, the compensation system should be an effective tool for creating desired employee behavior and positive attitudes within the organization (Beck-Krala and Scott, 2014).

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According to Chen and Hsieh (2006, p. 66), rewards are “everything employees perceive to be of value resulting from the employment relationship”. In addition, Armstrong, et al., (2011) defined rewards as a strategy, policies, and operations pursued by the company to ensure that the value of people and the contribution they make to achieving organization goals. Lim and Ling (2012) represented a reward as a system that consists of rewards and benefits that are given to employees. Such rewards are vacation holidays, health insurance, and transportation allowance and reward performance.

The functions of using rewards have been studied extensively as rewards can attract, retain, and motivate employees (Zhou, et al., 2011). They can also, effects the performance of employees and it has a positive impact on performance, experience, qualification, and seniority (Lim and Ling, 2012). In addition, rewards play a key role to fulfill goals and support strategy of organization (Klimkiewicz and Beck-Krala, 2015).Also, rewards can enhance the job satisfaction and commitment of an employee whether he is working in any type of organization (Malhotra, et al., 2007). Finally, Rewards can empower commitment and engagement, and they provide many opportunities for the contributions of people to be valued and recognized (Baeten, 2010).

Total Quality Management Practices

The significance of total quality management in business organizations has risen significantly over the past 20 years (Farshid and Amir, 2016). Due to increasing levels of competition in the global marketplace, the component of quality has become highly valued by organizations; this is in turn has resulted in TQM becoming a key management issue (Alamri, et al., 2014).

There are many studies tackled total quality management in Japan, United States, Europe, and developing countries (Zakuan, et al., 2010). There is no single uniformly accepted approach to TQM (Boon, et al., 2007). Many definitions exist for the term. Regarding quality, Ebert and Griffin (2005) defined it as a management approach focused on the development of all process, job, resource, output, person, time and place. In addition, Mohammed, et al., (2016) considered total quality management as one of modern philosophies in the world of administration, which includes a range of modern concepts that are based on the basic administrative means and innovative efforts and skills that improve performance and maintain the continuous improvement. For that there are those who know the total quality management as excellence it and excel, others see it as reducing defects in products or services, and some believe it to avoid accumulated losses Thus, the definition depends on the objectives of the organization (Mohammed, et al., 2016).

Among the benefits of total quality management improved management effectiveness, flexibility, competitiveness (Ebert and Griffin, 2005), improved organizational performance (Rahman and Bullock, 2005), and organization success via customer satisfaction and shared benefits by all members of the organization and to society (Whatiskt, 2014). Based on the comprehensive literature review, the present study focuses on the following five TQM practices; leadership, continuous improvement, customer satisfaction, employee empowerment, and strategic planning, these practices were defined as the most widely used by services organizations.

Leadership

Leadership is an important factor in the system of TQM both during its implementation and after the completion of the system in the process of continuous improvement (Sălăgean, 2014). According to Nwabueze (2011), leadership is described as being totally responsible for the success of the implementation of the TQM programs.

Leadership is one of the basic and the most important requirements in every organization as it creates the vision of the organization and ensures the actualization of the vision through execution. Moreover, leadership develops a long-term vision for the organization and guides the organization through the plan as it is motivated by ever changing customer wants (Ulle and Kumar, 2014). In other words, leaders have a vision of what can be achieved, and then they strive to deliver vision this to others while also ensuring that their strategies are constantly in line with the realization of their vision. In addition, leaders are responsible for motivating their entire organization, and they should have the ability to negotiate for resources as well as other support in order to achieve their goals.

The topic of leadership has been examined extensively by various scholars, such as Sharma and Jain (2013, p.310) who defined leadership as “a process by which a person influences others to accomplish an objective and directs the organization in a way that makes it more cohesive and coherent”. Similarly, Northouse (2010) viewed leadership as a process by which a person influences others to achieve common goal. Sălăgean (2014) also provided a definition for leadership, in which he calls the most important resource that holds in the absence of which all other resources, and it manages to cope with changes. Helmrich (2015) also described leaders as people who know how to realize objectives and encourage people along the way.

Leadership has an important effect on organizational performance (Fening, et al., 2008). It creates an organizational climate that empowers employees (Ugboro and Obeng, 2000). It also develops systems in order to meet customer expectations, thereby improving organizational performance (Fuentes, et al., 2006). Leadership is often considered the solution to most organizational issues because it can control human resources toward the strategic objectives of the organization and guarantee that organizational functions are coincide with external environments (Ulle and Kumar, 2014).

Continuous Improvement

There has been numerous changes in the business environment over the last several decades, organization must understand how work to improve performance (Roghianian, et al., 2012). Therefore, this concept has effectively employed to realize fundamental improvements of performance in the organization, thereby leading the organizations successfully in the highly competitive environment (Patidar, et al., 2016).

Since the core of strategic planning in any organization is to improve the productivity value, improving competitive image of the organization, improving overall effectiveness, reducing cost, reducing operator mistakes, eliminating waste, and maintaining health and safety standards, continuous improvement plays a very important role in long run (Singh and Singh, 2014). Therefore, continuous improvement on a larger scale within the organization becomes necessary. For this reason, a number of continuous improvement

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methodologies have been developed based on quality, the process of improvement, or both; the aim of these system is to reduce waste, simplify the production line and improve quality.

Caroly, et al. (2010), defined continuous improvement as a process that aims to control production costs and improve quality through optimize information, physical flows, and products. Chen, et al. (2010, p. 1070), he described continuous improvements as the “continuous identification and elimination of waste”. Another definition for continuous improvement is provided by Shafeek (2014), Shafeek call it is an ongoing effort to improve maintenance aimed at maintenance process simplification and reduction or elimination of maintenance process waste.

According to Struckman and Yammarino (2003), continuous improvement encourages an organization to undergo a learning process to develop and select optimal solutions to problems. Other benefits can be obtained by implementing continuous improvement are related to the financial performance of the organization. For instance, Saloni and Dyk (2009) suggested that continuous improvement can allow companies to reduce inventory waste, decrease manufacturing cycle times and labor, increase service quality and product quality in facilities by, positively impacting profits, system flexibility, cash flow, and delivery accuracy. Benefits can also be gained by implementing continuous improvement on organizational culture and employee satisfaction (Sánchez, 2012).

Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is one of the critical success factors in today’s competitive business environment as it influences companies’ market share and customer retention (Ooi, et al., 2011). Customers are often considered to be the most important asset of any organization; thus, the success of an organization depends on its number of customers (Iakov, 2013).

Customer satisfaction was related to people who paid for a products or services and used the products and services (Ling, et al., 2016). It is referring to how a product satisfies customers or how it fulfills their needs and expectations (Bitner and Zeithaml, 2003). Qi, et al. (2012) defined customer satisfaction as the comparison between expectations and the perceived performance after a specific purchase. Therefore, customer satisfaction is believed a positive determinant of how strong is the relationship between the customer and the product provider (Saleh, 2015).

According to Akenbor (2014), there are several basic questions that should be asked by a company in measuring and tracking customer satisfaction; How satisfied are the customers?, are the customers more satisfied or less satisfied with the company than they were in previous years?, how does the customer satisfaction level compare with that of the competitors?, what impact does their satisfaction level have on our company’s profit?.

Customer satisfaction is considered to be the baseline of standardization and the excellence of performance for many businesses. In addition, customer satisfaction also promotes product loyalty and good will for increase in product quality (Hilal, 2014). When customer satisfaction results are monitored over time, they can provide

comparisons to other organizations and can also help the company to determine the effectiveness of their business practices (Lieska, 2011). Moreover, satisfied customers have significant impact on the profits of business (Sabir, et al., 2014). This was supported before by Molinari, et al. (2008) who explains that customer satisfaction is associated with high customer loyalty, future purchases, and positive verbal communication.

Employee Empowerment

Employees are seen to possess a certain kind of power, and their potential can be released through empowerment by an increase of knowledge, experience and motivation (Darvish and Norozi, 2011; AlHrassi, et al., 2016; Obeidat, et al., 2016a, b, 2019; Abualoush, et al., 2018a, b; Al-dalahmeh, et al., 2018; Masa'deh, et al., 2018a, b). The first definition on empowerment can be traced back to 1788 when it was seen as the delegation in an organizations role which should be assigned to an individual based on their organizational role (Rezaie and Bagheri, 2014). Empowerment is also seen as the ability to allow others to assume the responsibilities, risks, and rewards that are linked with making their own decisions (Armache, 2013). According to Reji (2011), employee empowerment includes confidence, influence, information involvement, decision making and liability. Moreover, Ukil (2016) believed that empowerment not only involves giving power to the people to decide; he also highlights that empowerment is a kind of clever decision-making power that can be used for helping the company with their activities effectively. Individuals need to be empowered in order to perform their assigned tasks effectively. Therefore, empowerment should be at the core of any successful organizational strategy (Awamleh, 2013). A successful application of empowerment depends on both managers and subordinates.

Employee empowerment as a strategy that enhance organizational performance; it also helps with developing a flexible organization that can be capable of adapting to a changing external environment (Ferit, 2015). When employees experience empowerment and see the impact of their jobs are having on the organization, they identify more with the goals of the organization and as a result are more committed to it (Elloy, 2012). Similarly, it has been observed that employee empowerment is important to organizational innovativeness and effectiveness; with the right individuals, job characteristics and organizational environment, employee empowerment can have a noticeable effect on motivation and performance (Kimolo, 2013). Thus, employee empowerments can also improve productivity, performance and job satisfaction (Greasley, et al., 2005). Chaturvedi (2008) claimed that empowerment is one of the most effective ways of enabling employees at all levels to use their creative abilities to improve both the performance of the organization as well as the quality of their own working life.

Strategic Planning

In the present, strategic planning for all industries has become absolutely crucial, as there appears to be unprecedented phenomenon where every sector is being confronted with substantial increases in both uncertainty and competition (Vel, et al., 2012). All types of profit or non-profit organizations are seen to be involved in a strategic planning process (Hough, et al., 2011). Strategic planning deals with making long-term decision that help organization to respond to changing environments (Volberda, 2010). Suklev

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and Debarliev (2015) described strategic planning as activities that are geared towards obtaining success and remaining competitive in any sector. An appropriate strategic plan helps organization to change their plans according to market needs; it focuses on the organizational planning process (Brah and Lim, 2006).

McNamara (2016) defined strategic planning as a disciplined approach to producing fundamental decisions and actions that gives guidance and direction to members of an organization with particular emphasis to their role of products and services delivery. According to Rahman (2016), strategic planning its principle is collaborative and flexible in order to create and describe a better future and to address diversity of problem. In addition, David (2013) described strategic planning is a process of accomplishing the established vision, mission, and goals of the organization.

The objective of strategic planning is to achieve a balance between the external environment and the internal capabilities of the firm. For this purpose, the strategic managers identify critical tasks through a process which is known as the strategic management process (Pearce and Robinson, 2009; Jofre, 2011). This process is the approach currently used by strategic planners, and it consists of several phases. Such phases are analysis, formulation, implementation, evaluation and control (Ololube, et al., 2016).

Competitive Advantage

The business sector is currently experiencing intensive competition with both local and international players in the market; if businesses fail to deal with these changes, they are likely to lose substantial market share and profit. Finding a suitable position in an intensively competitive environment is the key to survival and long-term profitability for a business, and this goal is only possible through creating and keeping competitive advantage (Gareche, et al., 2013). Currently, all the market players are fighting for their share in a highly competitive environment, but only a few market leaders are focusing on the competition; therefore, these leaders are able to survive while the others die out (Essays, 2013).

The term competitive advantage refers to a “set of capabilities that permanently enable the business to demonstrate better performance than its competitors” (Bobillo, et al., 2010, p. 607). Ferrell (2012) suggested that competitive advantage is something that the company does better than its rival that give it increase customers satisfaction and develop relationships with important stakeholders. Yaseen, et al. (2016) defined competitive advantage as the capacity of an organization to create and maintain defensible position over its competitors.

According to Okonda, et al. (2016), competitive advantage is necessary for satisfied customers who wish to receive a higher value in delivered products for a higher income compared to what the owners request from management; such wants can be achieved through the organization of production, a higher application and production costs that are as low as possible. This goal may be attained either from implementing a value creating strategy that has not been implemented by other competitors or by implementing the same strategies used by the competitors but in a superior way.

Competitive advantage that are maintained for long periods of time can turn into strategic or sustainable competitive advantage (Popa, et al., 2011).

The main source for obtaining competitive advantage is by making the highest-quality product or achieving lower costs than rivals (Porter, 2013). Other sources include developing critical internal and external business relationships, as well as building a reputation for product quality (Sachitra and Chong, 2016). Both human capital and the evolution of information may also represent a source of competitive advantage (Popa, et al., 2011).

According to Durmus (2010), competitive advantage is consisted of approaches that a firm has adapted to buyers and improves performance on competitive markets. He also claims that companies can use one of the strategic approaches to compete with their rivals and win a competitive edge in the marketplace. A competitive advantage can occur when the firm is able to deliver the same benefits as their competitors but at a lower cost, giving them a cost advantage; they can also gain an advantage when they deliver benefits that exceed those of competing products, showing a differentiation advantage (Dakare, 2015).

Differentiation

A differentiation strategy is usually developed around various features, such as product quality, technology, innovativeness, reliability, brand image, firm reputation, durability, and customer service, all of which should be difficult for competitors to imitate (Moses, 2010). An implementation of a differentiation strategy can help organization to achieve a competitive advantage over its competitors that the implementation can create entry barriers to potential entrants. These entry barriers can be set up by building customer and brand loyalty. Thus, organization that implements a differentiation strategy attains the benefit of price-inelastic demand for its product or service (Tanwar, 2013).

Differentiation includes creating products or services that are different from -and more attractive- than those of other competitors. This depends on the exact nature of both the industry and the products and services themselves (Rahman, 2011). This point is noted by Othman (2016), who states that differentiation strategies are based on offering buyers something unique or different that makes the firm's product or service distinct from that of competitors. Customers are likely ready to pay a premium price for a product that is distinct in an important way, such as having a better service, a superior quality or special appeal.

In the study by Wen-Cheng, et al. (2011), differentiation can also be seen when a business aims to differentiate itself within only one or a small number of broad market segments. The specific customer needs of the segments suggest that there is a chance to provide products that are clearly different from the competitors who may be aiming at a wider group of customers. The main advantage of differentiation is that consumers of differentiated products are less sensitive to prices. An added advantage is that strategies based on high quality may actually increase the potential market share that a company can gain. Finally, highly distinctive reputable products make it difficult for new entrants to compete with the existing firms already possess (Altaf and Khalil, 2016).

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Rao (2011) claimed that, there are some risks associated with differentiation. For instance, customers are becoming more knowledgeable and demanding about what they want, what genuine value is and what they are willing to pay. Unless the differentiation is based on some unique proprietary knowledge, skills, expertise or patent, a firm faces the threat of being outmaneuvered by rivals, who can package their product or service with similar features at a lesser loss. In this way, excessive differentiation can seriously affect the competitive advantage and that profitability of organization.

Cost Leadership

The cost leadership strategy a process that are taken to produce goods or services with features that are acceptable to customers at the cost, relatively lower than that of competitors (Ireland, et al., 2011). This strategy is based on a firm's ability to provide a product or service at a lower cost than its rivals (Abd Aziz and Samad, 2016). Therefore, firms that pursue a cost leadership strategy must continuously benchmark themselves against other rival firms in order to measure their relative cost and profitability position in the marketplace (Wen-Cheng, et al., 2011). Organizations can follow cost leadership strategy, when the market is composed of many price sensitive buyers, also when the customers don't give much importance for brand, price sensitivity and buyers have significant bargaining power (Abdullah, et al., 2009).

A cost leadership strategy aims to realize the least possible cost in a certain industry and avoid flaws and wastes through controlling secondary costs, resources supply or product distribution, or through increasing their capacity utilization and production efficiency (Chung, et al., 2010; Prajogo, 2007; Fuentes, et al., 2006).

Abdullah and Kaliappen (2016) list six key cost advantages or sources of cost advantages for firms that successfully adopt cost leadership; size differences and economies of scale, high capacity utilization, experience differences and learning-curve economies, differential low-cost access to productive inputs, and technological advantages independent of scale, and policy choices. According to Tanwar (2013), cost leadership is vulnerable to risks such as, technological change that erases past investments and out dates past learning, imitation by late entrants who have an advantage of low cost learning, lack of attention to the needs and preferences of customers due to excessive concerns for cost minimization, and unexpected inflation in costs that reduces the firm's ability to offset product differentiation through cost leadership.

The Effect of Human Management Practices on Total Quality Management Practices

In recent decades, there has been a significant interest regarding both TQM and HRM in management and business research due to their potential to affect a range of organizational and individual performances (Boon, et al., 2007; Teh, 2010). "Both HRM and TQM are rational, consistent and strengthened systems of practices where the overall result is greater than the application of any one part" (Alfalla-Luque et al., 2012, p. 66).

In implementing total quality management processes in an organization, the human resource department plays a major role in several areas. Such areas are developing and communicating the TQM vision, preparing the organizational details for the

implementation of TQM procedures, and providing necessary support to maintain the enthusiasm about TQM (Izvercian, et al., 2014). Kumar (2012) stated that TQM affects the strategy process at all levels. In terms of HRM, TQM has an impact on an organization's culture as well as its work organization, staffing and planning, performance appraisal and compensation, and training and development policies and practices.

Continuous quality improvement depends on the best use of the talents and abilities of a company's workforce. To achieve world class quality, it is imperative that a company empowers its workers. This can be achieved through creating the appropriate human resource development through training, employee membership, and involvement, building quality awareness among employees and motivating employees (Shahraki, et al., 2011). HRM is commonly practiced as a part of the overall organizational quality planning and indirectly planned for internal customer satisfaction, across organizational team working, training and career development and quality of working life (Essays, 2013).

Consequently, many of the recent empirical studies show the effect of HRM practices on TQM practices. For instance, Li and Yang (2008) discussed how system quality can be improved through the service system and HR practices. Since most service industries involve interaction between personnel and customers in providing services, the enhancement of HR practices through training and the maintenance of personnel job attitude and service ability is more highly regarded. Their study reveals that TQM in the service industry stresses a sound design at the system level, and TQM is at its best when integrated with designs in HR practices. This results in better job attitude and enhancements in service ability, which in turn mean excellent service quality, more satisfied customers, and an improved organization performance. Abu-Doleh (2012) examined several key features namely training and development, employee career development, and recruiting and selection which appear to have the greatest influence on the implementation of TQM practices. According to Abu-Doleh (2012), HRM practices and TQM practices have a significant effect on organizational quality performance.

Silvia and Roberto (2012) conducted an empirical study to investigate the relationship between skill-developing HR practices and quality performance. They find that the skill-developing HR practices aimed at improving the interactions among all employees and developing multi-task knowledge could improve employees' capability to develop a more complete and multifaceted idea of the product by taking into consideration different needs. Thus, the socialization of HR practices is shown to enhance communication and the transfer of knowledge during the execution of the project, thereby contributing to a better understanding and better satisfaction of customers' requirements. Similarly, cross-training activities lead to higher product quality; it favors the integration of different competences and, encourages the ability to solve different problems.

Hatani and Mahrani (2013) showed how TQM significantly enhances the HRM practices. In testing the hypothesis, their result shows that TQM practices have positive and significant impact on HRM practices. This explanation for this is that implementation of TQM (at the height according to the prospects of employers) supports a good leadership, a compact team, employee engagement and the opening of information systems. In addition, Tripti and Singh (2015) discovered that HR mediates completely through

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leadership and quality culture practices for successful TQM implementation that enhances firm performance.

Total Quality Management Practices and Competitive Advantage

Quality management plays an important role in the overall organizational strategy. The key challenge for global organizations is to survive in this increasingly competitive global market (Zakuan, et al., 2010). Many studies indicate a positive relationship between TQM and competitive strategies, namely differentiation and cost leadership (Fuentes, et al., 2006; Lam, et al., 2011; Fernandez-Perez and Gutierrez-Gutierrez, 2013). Al-Rfou, et al. (2012) defined competitive advantage as the ability of an organization to create goods or services more efficiently than competitors do, thereby outperforming the competitors. Competitive advantage allows organizations to complete an increased level of its competitiveness and satisfy its customers; it is also a known sign of quality associated with cost, and it avoids wasting time and effort. When implementing TQM, operational performance improves. Since TQM aims at obtaining competitive advantage, it has been observed that the application of total quality management enhances competitiveness and improve customer satisfaction (Munizu, 2013).

According to Herzallah, et al. (2014), TQM could achieve competitive advantage because it is seen to bring about an improved financial performance, greater customer satisfaction, a faster response to competitive environment and improved product quality. As mentioned, TQM components move towards improved a firm's improved performance, such as greater levels of customer satisfaction, process improvement, and business performance. This in turn generates competitive advantage for firms (Jung, 2009). In addition, TQM practices enhanced competitive advantage. The effect of TQM practices in these aspects is of the utmost importance; thus, an effective implementation of TQM can produce improvements in the area of competitive abilities and provide strategic advances in the marketplace.

The goal of quality management is to decrease costs and improve customer satisfaction. These ideas fit with the market-based vision of competitive advantage arising from a superior cost structure or being able to differentiate products in a way that enhances value for customers; in addition, the reduced rework and savings that emerge from improving product quality can help lower a firm's cost structure, and producing products that better satisfy the requirements of customers creates, the possibility for differentiation (Friend, 2015).

Industries that adopt TQM can develop their competitive position; they can also achieve greater efficiency, greater differentiation of their products and greater achievement of their business (Herzallah, et al., 2014). Furthermore, there appears to be a significant relationship between TQM and business excellence where the continuous improvement of quality demonstrates the path to increases in stakeholder satisfaction, profitability, and market share; moreover, there are also decreases in manufacturing costs, which promotes industrial competitiveness (Rahman and Bullock, 2005). On the whole, organizations should be committed to TQM practices and their successful implementation (Al-Qudah, 2012).

Human Recourse Management Practices and Competitive Advantage

Traditional sources of competitive advantage, such as production capacities, research laboratories, access to financial resources, supply channels or economies of scale, are said to be necessary but inadequate for success in today's business environment. It is acknowledged that individuals are the key assets in the new world market and that all other assets are regarded merely as commodities which can be purchased at market prices; only the human asset is highly valued because it has potential to learn, grow, and contribute (Coff, 2011; Mirah and Masa'deh, 2014).

Competitive advantage can be developed and sustained by producing value in a way that is rare and difficult for competitors to imitate; the quality of the human resource should also be difficult to imitate (Pankaj, 2012). HRM practices such as performance appraisal, compensation, selection practices, employment security, job descriptions, career opportunities, and training and development practices can be clustered as a means to communicate to the employees regarding the specific skills and behaviors necessary to create and sustain a competitive advantage (Adil, 2015). If well managed, human resources have the potential to be a source of sustainable competitive advantage and have an impact on fundamental objectives such as quality, profits and customer satisfaction (Absar, et al., 2012). In addition, if HRM practices are used for improving competencies that are company specific and for creation of organizational knowledge, there is a possibility that competitive advantage can be sustained (Lazim, et al., 2015).

According to Mark (2011), HRM practices of an organization can be an important source of competitive advantage through cost leadership and product differentiation. The competitive advantage realized through HRM practices can be more sustainable than that achieved by other means. Therefore, a company should continuously improve its HRM practices to retain its competitive advantage. For this reason, human Resources seek to achieve this by aim the supply of skilled and qualified individuals and the capabilities of the current staff, with the organization's current and future business plans; this is done in order to maximize the return on investment, knowledge management and electronic systems (Aldmour, et al., 2015, 2017; Almajali and Al-Lozi, 2016; Alenezi, et al., 2017; Khwaldeh, et al., 2017; Obeidat, et al., 2017; Tarhini, et al., 2017a,b), and in turn ensure future survival and success (Wen-Cheng, et al., 2011; Obeidat, et al., 2019).

Conclusion

Previous empirical research investigated the effect of TQM practices on competitive advantage (Reed, et al., 2000; Douglas and Judge, 2001; Munizu, 2013). Another stream of research looks at the effect of HRM practices on competitive advantage (Takeuchi and Wakabayashi, 2003; Waiganjo, et al., 2012; Bhattacharjee and Bhattacharjee, 2015). Therefore, HRM practices and TQM practices are important for gaining competitive advantage (Usrofand Elmorsej, 2016). The telecommunication industry today is considered to be a very important component of productivity across economies and societies, as this industry is not only a significant sponsor towards the economic activities of countries but also to the development of other industries (Venkatram and Zhu, 2012). The telecommunication industry in Jordan has evolved at a rapid speed that is much similar to some other countries, and many new players have become newly active on the

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market, thereby creating intensive competition in this sector for the first time. Thus, companies are increasingly seeking for growth and innovation by developing more differentiating services and cost leadership (Musa, 2013).

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